

Instruct-ULTRA

Integrating Structural Biology

Instruct-ULTRA

WP 2 – Roadmap to the future for Instruct

Lead Beneficiary: P1-Instruct

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Deliverable D 2.1 Plan a programme for review of Instruct Infrastructure with external review panel.

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Project objective

To review the composition of Instruct's infrastructure facilities to take account of advances newly available in structural biology research.

Executive summary

D 2.1 report

Introduction

Instruct Centres and facilities were last externally reviewed in 2014, as part of the validation process for the application to become an ERIC. Since then there have been significant developments in structural biology most notably in cryo-Electron Microscopy. It is therefore timely that the technology services provided by Instruct are audited to assess what new technology should be added to the Instruct-ERIC portfolio and which services are no longer in demand. This links with Work Package 4 which involves a call for projects with the objective of introducing new and innovative technology into the portfolio of services provided by Instruct facilities to take account of advances newly available in structural biology research.

Background

Analysis of Instruct service/technology usage (2014-2017).

The number of user visits (requested, approved and completed) to access different technology services offered by Instruct are captured by the ARIA access management system. Analysis of these data provides information on the demand for the different service technologies offered by Instruct. The actual activity that is subsequently delivered depends on the time and cost of each service.

Following work of the Instruct Access Committee (REFS), a new hierarchical structure has been developed for presenting the service technology of Instruct to the user community which is detailed in Appendix 1. All services have been grouped into three broad categories, namely 3D Structural analysis, Biomolecular analysis and Sample Preparation. The distribution of access visits to these three categories for the last three years (2014-2017) is summarised in Appendix 2 a, which shows that sample preparation accounts for the largest proportion of access followed by 3D structural analysis and with biomolecular analysis. This might be expected as sample preparation is the first part of any workflow leading to structural or biophysical characterisation. The broad service technology categories can be further broken down into sub-categories and the distribution of access across these is shown in Appendix 2 b-d. From this analysis, the services that attract the largest proportion of user visits over the last three years are Protein production (30 %) and Cryo-EM (25%), both of which are offered by several Instruct Centres and for Cryo-EM the number has increased with the addition of the CEITEC EM Facility following the Czech Republic joining Instruct in 2016.

New Instruct service/technology (2014-2017).

In 2014, the Nanobody4Instruct Centre was established and has rapidly become a key service offered by Instruct with an average of 9 proposals submitted/year for construction of nanobodies to a variety of protein targets.

The range of biophysical techniques offered by Instruct has increased with the inclusion of Micro Scale Thermophoresis (MST). This is now used equally with the other established methods (e.g. Analytical Ultracentrifugation), showing how it has been assimilated into the portfolio of biophysical techniques offered by several Centres for biomolecular analysis.

Description of Work

Baseline assessment for future developments (January – April 2018)

The process for reviewing the portfolio of service technology provided by Instruct is summarised diagrammatically in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Schematic of review process

The Instruct-ERIC Executive committee will be advised of the terms of reference of the review. Information will be gathered from Instruct-ERIC centres by a questionnaire implemented in the Instruct ARIA proposal management system. The survey will request the following information from the Instruct Centres about their experience with the service technology offered to Instruct as follows:-

Aspect	Indicator
Demand	Size and geographical distribution of user base
Impact	Scientific highlights (linked publications)
Scope	No of different research areas enabled
Innovation	Relevant R & D activity

The survey will be conducted through ARIA and the questions are given in Appendix 3.

A meeting of Instruct-UTRA partners with the Science Advisory Board of the project has been arranged for 7th – 8th March 2017. Presentations covering current and future developments of Instruct service technology will be given by members of Instruct Centres. Ahead of the meeting a document summarising the results of the questionnaire sent to Instruct-ERIC Centres will be sent to SAB members. The SAB will be invited to comment on the current platforms and advise on where new developments should be considered. The feedback from the SAB will be reported to the Instruct-ERIC Executive as part of recommendations for future technology services to be adopted during the next 3 years. The Work Package 4 pilot projects will provide a mechanism for testing the robustness of new technology.

Appendices

Appendix 1 New structure for services catalogue

Group	Type
3D Structural Analysis	Electron Microscopy
	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
	X-Ray Approaches
Biomolecular analysis	Macromolecular Interactions
	Mass Spectrometry

	Sample Characterisation
Sample preparation	Crystallisation
	Nanobody Production
	Protein Production

Appendix 2 The percentage of Instruct visits for different service technologies (2014-2107)
 (a) Overall distribution (b) 3D structural analysis (c) Sample preparation (d) Biophysical analysis. (n =365).

Appendix 3 Centre Service technology Survey questions

1. What scope of bioscience areas is your research centre covering? Please tick all which are applicable.

Biotechnology
Biochemistry
Biomedical engineering
Biophysics
Cancer
Cell biology
Chemistry
Environmental science
Genetics
Immunology
Infectious disease
Microbiology
Molecular biology
Neurology
Pharmacology
Plant sciences
Structural Biology
Virology
Zoology
Other:

2. How is your research centre engaging in R&D currently?

For example new instrumentation, methods, software. Please give a short description for each area.

3. Please give 5-10 scientific highlights from your research centre over the last three years, which are linked to Instruct service technology platforms.

4. Which meetings / conferences in 2018 are you planning to attend where you could potentially represent Instruct-ERIC?

For example include slides about Instruct-ERIC at the end of a powerpoint presentation; recruit new people to sign-up during networking opportunities; consider manning an exhibition booth at key events.